

Supplementary Materials for "Robust Adaptive Kolmogorov-Arnold Neural Control"

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Abstract—This document collects the material supporting “Robust Adaptive Kolmogorov–Arnold Neural Control” that is referenced from, but not reproduced in, the main paper: the line-by-line derivation behind Theorem 1 and Corollaries 1–2, the discrete-time recursive-least-squares recursion, the Jacobian and input matrices of the benchmark used by the LTV-MPC baseline, and that baseline’s tuning configuration. These are technical complements; the main paper remains self-contained without them.

I. PLANT CONFIGURATION

The benchmark is Johansson’s quadruple-tank process [1], a nonlinear multivariable plant of four interconnected tanks and two pumps with strong cross-coupling and a selectable non-minimum-phase (NMP) regime [2]. The full nonlinear model and its numerical parameters (areas $A_{1..4}$, $a_{1..4}$, pump gains $k_{1,2}$, valve ratios $\gamma_{1,2}$, and g) are stated in Section III of the main paper and are not repeated here.

For completeness of the LTV-MPC baseline, whose detailed tuning is given in the final section, linearizing the quadruple-tank model about the current operating point yields the state Jacobian A [1]:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{a_1}{A_1} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_1}} & 0 & \frac{a_3}{A_1} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_3}} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{a_2}{A_2} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_2}} & 0 & \frac{a_4}{A_2} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_4}} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{a_3}{A_3} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_3}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{a_4}{A_4} \sqrt{\frac{g}{2h_4}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

and the input matrix B :

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{A_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\gamma_2 k_2}{A_2} \\ 0 & \frac{(1-\gamma_2)k_2}{A_3} \\ \frac{(1-\gamma_1)k_1}{A_4} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The same B is the input map of the control-affine form $\dot{x} = f(x) + Bu$ analyzed in the main paper; it has full column rank at the NMP operating point, so the left pseudoinverse $B^+ = (B^T B)^{-1} B^T$ satisfies $B^+ B = I$. The plant schematic is shown in Fig. 1.

II. SYMBOLIC DISTILLATION AND NORMALIZATION

The explicit distilled control law $u_{1\text{raw}}, u_{2\text{raw}}$ obtained from the KAN, together with its variable key $x_{1..8}$, is now reported in-text in the controller-design section of the main paper and

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Fig. 1. **Quadruple-tank process.** As described, this plant features four interconnected tanks and two pumps and exhibits strong cross-coupling. A nontrivial approach is required for NMP configuration of the plant.

is therefore not reproduced here; the source GitHub is given as [3]. The distillation procedure itself follows the static-KAN identification of [4].

One implementation detail relevant to reproducibility: the symbolic expressions were extracted on *normalized* inputs for the training stage, and were re-scaled to physical units in the experiments to ensure benchmark fairness. This normalization is also the mechanism that enforces the regressor bound $\|\Phi(x)\| \leq \Phi_{\max}$ on the compact operating set Ω which is invoked in the stability analysis below.

III. RECURSIVE LEAST SQUARES DISCRETE IMPLEMENTATION

This section records the discrete-time RLS recursion used in the implementation. The discrete covariance Γ_k below is the sampled counterpart of the continuous-time gain Γ that appears in the stability analysis; the discrete forgetting factor λ corresponds to the continuous forgetting rate $\rho \approx (1 - \lambda)/T_a$ entering the gain law $\dot{\Gamma} = \rho\Gamma - \Gamma\Phi\Phi^T\Gamma$ of Section IV.

For a system modeled as

$$y_k = \Phi_k^T \theta + \varepsilon_k, \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi_k \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the KAN-distilled nonlinear regressor evaluated at step k , θ the estimated linear weights, ε_k the approximation error, and y_k the target control signal, the weight estimate updates as

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \hat{\theta}_{k-1} + L_k (y_k - \hat{\theta}_{k-1}^T \Phi_k), \quad (4)$$

where the term $(y_k - \hat{\theta}_{k-1}^T \Phi_k)$ is the prediction error and L_k is the estimator gain

$$L_k = \Gamma_{k-1} \Phi_k (\lambda R_k + \Phi_k^T \Gamma_{k-1} \Phi_k)^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

with R_k the measurement-noise covariance and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ the forgetting factor. To maintain numerical stability and positive definiteness, the covariance is propagated in the Joseph-stabilized form

$$\Gamma_k = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left[(I - L_k \Phi_k^T) \Gamma_{k-1} (I - L_k \Phi_k^T)^T + L_k R_k L_k^T \right]. \quad (6)$$

When persistent excitation is absent, Γ_k is additionally held within $[\gamma_{\min} I, \gamma_{\max} I]$ by covariance bounding/resetting; this is the discrete realization of the uniform bound on Γ required by Corollary 2.

IV. STABILITY ANALYSIS

This section gives the line-by-line derivation behind Theorem 1 and Corollaries 1–2 of the main paper. The argument is conducted over the composite error state

$$\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} e \\ \tilde{\theta} \end{bmatrix}, \quad e = x - x_{\text{ref}}, \quad \tilde{\theta} = \hat{\theta} - \theta^*, \quad (7)$$

i.e. the tracking error stacked with the weight estimation error. The integral-state error $\tilde{d} = \hat{d} - d^*$ is deliberately *excluded* from ζ ; the reason is the central structural point of the analysis and is made precise below.

A. Lyapunov candidate

The candidate is taken over the tracking and weight channels only [5], [6]:

$$V(\zeta) = \frac{1}{2} e^T P e + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \tilde{\theta}, \quad (8)$$

with $P = P^T \succ 0$ the controller weighting matrix and $\Gamma = \Gamma^T \succ 0$ the RLS gain (kept uniformly bounded and uniformly positive definite by the forgetting/covariance mechanism of Section III). Since P and Γ^{-1} are symmetric positive definite, V is positive definite and radially unbounded, so there exist constants $c_1, c_2 > 0$ with

$$c_1 \|\zeta\|^2 \leq V(\zeta) \leq c_2 \|\zeta\|^2, \quad (9)$$

i.e. V satisfies class- \mathcal{K}_∞ bounds on ζ (Khalil Lemma 4.3 [7]).

Why \tilde{d} is not in V . The integral state is governed by

$$\dot{\tilde{d}} = K_I e, \quad K_I = k_I I \succ 0, \quad (10)$$

implemented with a standard anti-windup clamp: accumulation is frozen whenever it would drive \hat{d} outside a fixed band, so $\|\hat{d}(t)\| \leq \bar{d}$ for an explicit, known \bar{d} , for all t and by *construction of the update rule itself*. Together with $\|d^*\| \leq d_{\max}$ this yields the uniform bound

$$\|\tilde{d}(t)\| \leq \bar{d} + d_{\max} =: \bar{d}_{\text{tot}} \quad \forall t. \quad (11)$$

It is instructive to see what fails if one instead retains \tilde{d} inside the energy. Augmenting (8) with $\frac{1}{2} \bar{d}^T Q_I \tilde{d}$ and making the natural design choice $Q_I = P/k_I$ (so that $K_I = Q_I^{-1} P = k_I I$), the integral cross-term becomes

$$\bar{d}^T Q_I \dot{\tilde{d}} = \bar{d}^T Q_I K_I e = \bar{d}^T P e, \quad (12)$$

which cancels the $-e^T P \bar{d}$ term arising from $e^T P \dot{e}$ exactly. After this cancellation \tilde{d} no longer appears anywhere in

\dot{V} : the integral coordinate is left with no dissipation term. A pure integrator driven by a non-vanishing disturbance is precisely the windup configuration, so this is exactly where the physics would bite. The contrast with the weight channel is structural: the RLS forgetting term makes Γ^{-1} decay at rate ρ , and that decay—acting through the metric of V itself, not through any explicit pull-to-zero in $\dot{\tilde{\theta}}$ —supplies a genuine negative term in \dot{V} (the implicit leakage of (27) below). The integrator (10) carries a *constant* gain K_I and admits no such mechanism. We therefore keep \tilde{d} out of V and certify its boundedness by the clamp (11), treating it thereafter as a bounded exogenous signal alongside δ .

B. Error dynamics

On the operating set the plant nonlinearity is captured by the distilled model

$$f(x) = \Phi(x)^T \theta^* + \varepsilon(x), \quad \varepsilon(x) = d^* + \delta(x), \quad (13)$$

where θ^* are the (unknown, constant) ideal weights, d^* is the constant bias, and $\delta(x)$ collects the bounded time-varying terms—time-varying approximation error, the underactuation residual $(BB^+ - I)(\cdot)$, the slew-saturation residual, and the UKF state-estimation residual—so that $\delta \in \mathcal{L}_\infty$. The error derivative is

$$\dot{e} = \dot{x} - \dot{x}_{\text{ref}} = \Phi(x)^T \theta^* + d^* + \delta(x) + Bu - \dot{x}_{\text{ref}}. \quad (14)$$

The unsaturated command is

$$u = B^+ (\dot{x}_{\text{ref}} - Ke - \Phi(x)^T \hat{\theta} - \hat{d}), \quad K = K_P + \bar{K}_L, \quad (15)$$

with $B^+ = (B^T B)^{-1} B^T$ the left pseudoinverse ($B \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 2}$ has full column rank at the NMP operating point), $\hat{\theta}, \hat{d}$ the estimated weights and integral state, and $\bar{K}_L = K_L/e_{\max}$ the Lipschitz-shaping gain folded into the total proportional gain K .

Remark: The left pseudoinverse minimizes the control effort $\|u\|$ in the least-squares sense, consistent with the Lipschitz constraint enforced on the control law.

Substituting (15) into (14) and using $BB^+ \approx I$, with the projection residual $(BB^+ - I)(\cdot)$ absorbed into δ ,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e} &= \Phi^T \theta^* + d^* + \delta + BB^+ (\dot{x}_{\text{ref}} - Ke - \Phi^T \hat{\theta} - \hat{d}) - \dot{x}_{\text{ref}} \\ &= \Phi^T (\theta^* - \hat{\theta}) + (d^* - \hat{d}) - Ke + \delta. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Setting $\theta^* - \hat{\theta} = -\tilde{\theta}$ and $d^* - \hat{d} = -\tilde{d}$,

$$\dot{e} = -\Phi^T \tilde{\theta} - \tilde{d} - Ke + \delta. \quad (17)$$

The two exogenous terms are now grouped into a single *effective disturbance*

$$\omega(t) := \delta(x(t), t) - \tilde{d}(t), \quad (18)$$

which is legitimate precisely because \tilde{d} is bounded by *construction* (11) rather than by anything proved below. Hence ω is a bona-fide bounded input,

$$\|\omega(t)\| \leq \|\delta\|_\infty + \bar{d}_{\text{tot}} =: \Delta < \infty, \quad (19)$$

uniformly in t , and the error dynamics reduce to

$$\dot{e} = -\Phi^T \tilde{\theta} - Ke + \omega. \quad (20)$$

C. Time derivative of the Lyapunov function

Since θ^* is constant, $\dot{\tilde{\theta}} = \dot{\hat{\theta}}$. Differentiating (8) and using the symmetry of P and Γ^{-1} [8],

$$\dot{V} = e^T P \dot{e} + \tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\tilde{\theta}} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\theta}^T \frac{d}{dt} (\Gamma^{-1}) \tilde{\theta}. \quad (21)$$

Weight adaptation law. The RLS update is chosen so that the weight cross-term cancels. Substituting (20) into the first term of (21) produces $-e^T P \Phi^T \tilde{\theta}$; requiring it to cancel against $\tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\tilde{\theta}}$, and using $e^T P \Phi^T \tilde{\theta} = \tilde{\theta}^T \Phi P e$,

$$\begin{aligned} -\tilde{\theta}^T \Phi P e + \tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\tilde{\theta}} &= 0 \\ \Gamma^{-1} \dot{\tilde{\theta}} &= \Phi P e \implies \dot{\tilde{\theta}} = \hat{\theta} = \Gamma \Phi P e. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Inverse-covariance derivative. The continuous-time gain law with forgetting [5] is

$$\dot{\Gamma} = \rho \Gamma - \Gamma \Phi \Phi^T \Gamma, \quad \rho \approx \frac{1 - \lambda}{T_a}, \quad (23)$$

where λ is the discrete forgetting factor and T_a the adaptation interval. Differentiating $\Gamma \Gamma^{-1} = I$ and substituting (23),

$$\begin{aligned} 0 = \dot{\Gamma} \Gamma^{-1} + \Gamma \frac{d}{dt} (\Gamma^{-1}) &= (\rho \Gamma - \Gamma \Phi \Phi^T \Gamma) \Gamma^{-1} + \Gamma \frac{d}{dt} (\Gamma^{-1}) \\ &= \rho I - \Gamma \Phi \Phi^T + \Gamma \frac{d}{dt} (\Gamma^{-1}), \end{aligned}$$

and hence, since Γ is invertible,

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\Gamma^{-1}) = \Phi \Phi^T - \rho \Gamma^{-1}. \quad (24)$$

Reduced derivative. Substituting (20), (22), and (24) into (21), the weight cross-term cancels exactly— $\tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \Gamma \Phi P e = \tilde{\theta}^T \Phi P e$ annihilates $-e^T P \Phi^T \tilde{\theta}$ —and the $-e^T P \dot{d}$ that would otherwise appear in (17) is now carried inside $e^T P \omega$. What remains is

$$\dot{V} = -e^T P K e + e^T P \omega + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\theta}^T \Phi \Phi^T \tilde{\theta} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \tilde{\theta}. \quad (25)$$

No cross-term in \tilde{d} remains to be cancelled or bounded, because \tilde{d} was never placed in V ; its only trace on the loop is the bounded forcing ω , exactly as δ .

D. Bounding the indefinite terms

Disturbance term. By Cauchy–Schwarz and Young’s inequality, for $\mu > 0$,

$$e^T P \omega \leq \lambda_{\max}(P) \|e\| \|\omega\| \leq \frac{\mu}{2} \|e\|^2 + \frac{\lambda_{\max}(P)}{2\mu} \|\omega\|^2. \quad (26)$$

Weight term (implicit leakage). With $\|\Phi(x)\| \leq \Phi_{\max}$ on the compact set Ω (enforced by input normalization and feature bounding), $\frac{1}{2} \tilde{\theta}^T \Phi \Phi^T \tilde{\theta} \leq \frac{1}{2} \Phi_{\max}^2 \|\tilde{\theta}\|^2$, so combining with the forgetting term,

$$\frac{1}{2} \tilde{\theta}^T \Phi \Phi^T \tilde{\theta} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \tilde{\theta}^T \Gamma^{-1} \tilde{\theta} \leq -\frac{1}{2} (\rho \lambda_{\min}(\Gamma^{-1}) - \Phi_{\max}^2) \|\tilde{\theta}\|^2. \quad (27)$$

This negative term is the metric decay of exponential forgetting: Γ^{-1} shrinking at rate ρ damps $\tilde{\theta}$ through the geometry of V itself, provided Γ^{-1} stays bounded away from zero. The integrator (10) admits no analogue— K_I is constant—which is exactly why \tilde{d} is handled by the clamp (11) and not here.

Sign conditions. Positive definiteness of the error term requires $\lambda_{\min}(PK) > \mu/2$; choose $\mu = \lambda_{\min}(PK)$. Taking the gains scalar, $K = kI$ with $k = k_P + \bar{k}_L > 0$, gives $PK = kP \succ 0$

and $\lambda_{\min}(PK) = k \lambda_{\min}(P)$ (more generally, it suffices that $PK + K^T P \succ 0$). The weight term is negative under the damping condition

$$\rho \lambda_{\min}(\Gamma^{-1}) > \Phi_{\max}^2, \quad (28)$$

which is enforceable since Φ_{\max} is finite (normalization, state bounds, slew limiting) and Γ^{-1} is bounded and uniformly positive definite.

E. Dissipation inequality

Collecting (26)–(27), the time derivative satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} \leq & -(\lambda_{\min}(PK) - \frac{\mu}{2}) \|e\|^2 \\ & - \frac{1}{2} (\rho \lambda_{\min}(\Gamma^{-1}) - \Phi_{\max}^2) \|\tilde{\theta}\|^2 + \frac{\lambda_{\max}(P)}{2\mu} \|\omega\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Defining

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &:= \min \left\{ \lambda_{\min}(PK) - \frac{\mu}{2}, \frac{1}{2} (\rho \lambda_{\min}(\Gamma^{-1}) - \Phi_{\max}^2) \right\}, \\ \gamma &:= \frac{\lambda_{\max}(P)}{2\mu}, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

both positive under (28), and using $\|\zeta\|^2 = \|e\|^2 + \|\tilde{\theta}\|^2$, inequality (29) reads

$$\dot{V} \leq -\alpha \|\zeta\|^2 + \gamma \|\omega\|^2, \quad (31)$$

a dissipation inequality on the *same* vector ζ bounded in (9), with ω from (18) satisfying $\|\omega\|_{\infty} \leq \Delta$.

Theorem 1 (Stability of LCA-RLS-KAN). *Consider the closed-loop system formed by the plant and the LCA-RLS-KAN controller (15), (22), with integral update (10) implemented under the anti-windup clamp (11). Let P, Γ be symmetric positive definite and $K = kI \succ 0$, with Γ kept uniformly bounded and uniformly positive definite. Assume the ideal weights are bounded ($\|\theta^*\| \leq \theta_{\max}$) and the lumped disturbance is bounded ($\delta \in \mathcal{L}_{\infty}$), so ω in (18) satisfies $\omega \in \mathcal{L}_{\infty}$. If the damping condition (28) holds, then with α, γ in (30),*

$$\dot{V} \leq -\alpha \|\zeta\|^2 + \gamma \|\omega\|^2.$$

By the class- \mathcal{H}_{∞} bounds (9), V is an ISS-Lyapunov function (Khalil Definition 4.7, Theorem 4.19 [7]); hence the $(e, \tilde{\theta})$ -subsystem is Input-to-State Stable with respect to ω , and ζ is Globally Uniformly Ultimately Bounded (GUUB), converging to the residual set

$$\mathcal{R} = \left\{ \zeta : \|\zeta\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{c_2}{c_1} \frac{\gamma}{\alpha} \Delta} \right\}. \quad (32)$$

The integral-state error \tilde{d} is bounded independently by \bar{d}_{tot} (11), so the full triple $(e, \tilde{\theta}, \tilde{d})$ remains bounded for all t .

Corollary 1 (Practical Tracking Accuracy). *Suppose the distilled basis captures the plant nonlinearity exactly, so the approximation error vanishes ($\varepsilon \equiv 0$, hence $\delta \equiv 0$), and there is no constant bias ($d^* = 0$). Then (18) gives $\omega = -\tilde{d}$, so $\|\omega\|_{\infty} \leq \bar{d}_{\text{tot}}$ by (11) alone—the residual disturbance entering the proof is governed entirely by the tightness of the anti-windup clamp, with no remaining contribution from δ . By (32), the tracking error converges to*

$$\|e(t)\| \lesssim \sqrt{\frac{c_2}{c_1} \frac{\gamma}{\alpha} \bar{d}_{\text{tot}}} \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow \infty.$$

Exact asymptotic tracking ($\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e(t) = 0$) is not claimed: with a non-leaky integrator (10), \bar{d} need not vanish even when $\delta \equiv 0$ —it merely stays clamped. The corollary instead makes explicit that the achievable tracking accuracy in the ideal case is a designer-controllable quantity, set directly by the anti-windup bound \bar{d} : a tighter clamp tightens the guaranteed accuracy, at the usual cost of a less aggressive integrator.

Corollary 2 (Robustness to Lack of Excitation). *Under the conditions of Theorem 1, the error state ζ remains GUUB even in the absence of persistent excitation (PE).*

Proof. Absent PE, constant-forgetting RLS alone need not keep Γ upper bounded—the $\rho\Gamma$ growth term in (23) is unopposed as $\Phi \rightarrow 0$. The covariance-bounding/resetting mechanism of Section III enforces $\gamma_{\min}I \preceq \Gamma(t) \preceq \gamma_{\max}I$, so Γ^{-1} stays bounded and the damping condition (28) continues to hold; consequently the bound (29) is unaffected by the loss of excitation. The weight error $\tilde{\theta}$ then merely fails to converge to zero but stays in a bounded set, and ISS of (31) preserves GUUB of ζ [6]. \square

V. LINEAR TIME-VARYING MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL TUNING CONFIGURATION

Affine Linear Time-Varying Model Predictive Control had been tuned according to the state-input tuning guidelines previously established in literature [9], [10], with mathematical configuration provided below:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu + d_{lin}$$

where matrix A is the Jacobian matrix A given in Section I, matrix B is evaluated by Johansson [1] and additionally provided in Section I and d_{lin} represents the linearization offset.

Matrix Q was tuned as:

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} 40 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 40 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Matrix R was tuned as:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.001 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.001 \end{pmatrix}$$

The structure followed the Linear Time-Varying methodology, re-linearizing the plant every discrete time interval. The prediction horizon is $N = 30$.

The model was re-linearized at each sampling instant about the current state estimate \hat{x}_k using Euler discretization with sampling time $dt = 0.003s$, while the prediction model was discretized with interval $\Delta t_p = 0.1s$ to reduce optimization complexity.

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